

A journey into binary classification challenges in AI

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Context

Artificial Intelligence

Machine Learning

Supervised Learning

Predict a feature

Classification

Predict a category

Regression

Predict a continuous numeric feature

Unsupervised Learning

Discover structure in the data

Dimensionality Reduction

Reduce the number of features

Clustering

Find groups of similar individuals

Other Machine Learning Approaches

Other AI Approaches

PhD at the Gasser Lab - UniMelb

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Research review paper

Harnessing model organism genomics to underpin the machine learning-based prediction of essential genes in eukaryotes – Biotechnological implications

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1. Know your problem, data and potential bias

↓ Critical!

2. Features: collection, engineering, selection

	Features		Label
	size	edge	color
Observations	small	dotted	green
	big	striped	yellow
	medium	normal	green

3. Split the data: cross-validation and testing

4. Try multiple algorithms (and parameters)

Common Classification Machine Learning Algorithms

Non-Brand Data

<p>Logistic Regression</p> $P(y=1 x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n)}}$	<p>Random Forest</p> $\hat{f}(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B f_b(x)$	<p>K-NN</p> $d(x, x') = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x'_i)^2}$
<p>Decision Tree</p> $\text{Gini}(t) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^c p_i^2 \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Entropy}(t) = - \sum_{i=1}^c p_i \log(p_i)$	<p>Isolation Forest</p> $s(x, n) = 2^{-\frac{E(h(x))}{c(n)}}$	<p>SVM</p> $f(x) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b \right)$
<p>Gradient Boosting</p> $F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \eta h_m(x)$	<p>Naive Bayes</p> $P(y x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{P(y) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i y)}{P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}$	<p>NN</p> $a^{(l)} = g(W^{(l)} a^{(l-1)} + b^{(l)})$

5. Choose adequate metrics

Confusion Matrix:

Table showing correct and incorrect predictions for each class.

- Helps understand what types of errors the model is making. Threshold-depender

Accuracy:

Proportion of correct predictions out of all predictions made.

- Good when classes are balanced.

Precision:

Proportion of true positives out of all predicted positives.

- Important when the cost of false positives is high (e.g., wrong diagnosis).

Recall (Sensitivity):

Proportion of true positives identified out of all actual positives.

- Relevant when missing positive cases is more serious (e.g., cancer).

F1-Score:

Harmonic mean of precision and recall.

- Useful when classes are imbalanced and a balance between precision and recall is needed. Useful for comparing models.

AUC-ROC/AUC-PR (Area Under the ROC/PR Curve):

Measures the model's ability to distinguish between classes.

- Closer to 1 means better separation. AUC-PR recommended for imbalanced datasets

		Predicted Class		
		Positive	Negative	
Actual Class	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN) Type II Error	Sensitivity $\frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}$
	Negative	False Positive (FP) Type I Error	True Negative (TN)	Specificity $\frac{TN}{(TN + FP)}$
		Precision $\frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}$	Negative Predictive Value $\frac{TN}{(TN + FN)}$	Accuracy $\frac{TP + TN}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)}$

6. Class imbalance requires attention

7. Underfitting vs. overfitting

	Underfitting	Just right	Overfitting
Symptoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- High training error- Training error close to test error- High bias	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Training error slightly lower than test error	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Low training error- Training error much lower than test error- High variance
Regression			
Classification			
Deep learning			
Remedies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Complexify model- Add more features- Train longer		<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Regularize- Get more data

8. Model interpretation

Feature Importance in Random Forest

9. Biological interpretation

Han (2008)

10. Concluding remarks

- Understand the problem, data quality, and biases
- Address class imbalance to avoid misleading results
- Balance model complexity to prevent overfitting and underfitting
- Engineer and select meaningful features with biological relevance
- Split data and use cross-validation for reliable evaluation
- Try multiple algorithms and tune parameters for best fit
- Define appropriate metrics aligned with real-world goals
- Interpret models carefully, linking results to biological context
- Collaborate with domain experts for meaningful insights
- Integrate AI and biology to drive trustworthy discoveries and decisions

